

Methane Emissions from Field Dumping of Oil Palm Empty Fruit Bunch (EFB)

A Field Survey of Decomposition and Methane Generation, with a Solid-Waste-Disposal Emissions Baseline

D. Spagnuolo, A. Broughton

Article 4 of a series on the characterisation and valorisation of oil palm empty fruit bunch

10.5281/zenodo.20528440

Abstract

The most common fate of oil palm empty fruit bunch (EFB) is dumping in the plantation fields, where it is tipped in piles and windrows along field roads and left to decompose. This article reports a field survey of seven EFB dumping sites in West Kalimantan, Indonesia, visited between September and November 2024, in which the age, dimensions, state of decomposition and in-pile methane concentration of each dump were recorded. The survey shows that a dumped pile passes through a predictable sequence: an initial aerobic phase of one to two months, marked by fungal colonisation and self-heating and producing no methane, followed by an anaerobic phase from roughly two to nine months during which methane is generated, and finally a stabilised state by nine to twelve months in which methane is no longer detectable. In-pile methane concentrations of up to 24,866 ppm (2.5 % by volume) were measured during the anaerobic phase. The methane emission from field dumping is quantified using the UNFCCC Methodological Tool 04, "Emissions from solid waste disposal sites", with EFB classified as garden-type waste. For a standard 60 t h⁻¹ mill disposing of approximately 66,676 tonnes of EFB per year, the first-order decay model gives, at the methodology default decay rate of 0.17 yr⁻¹, a first-year emission of about 1,400 t CO₂e that, under continuous year-on-year dumping, accumulates to a steady state of approximately 9,000 t CO₂e per year. The field evidence, however, is that the piles decompose almost completely within nine to twelve months — an effective decay rate closer to 1.0 yr⁻¹ — which front-loads the same total emission into the first few years and, over a thirty-year crediting period, raises the cumulative emission by roughly a fifth. The discrepancy between the methodology default and the observed decay rate is examined in detail, and a revision of the parameter for EFB is recommended.

1. Introduction

Earlier articles in this series characterised EFB as a feedstock, demonstrated its conversion to a fermentable hydrolysate, and quantified the methane baseline of a large dedicated solid waste disposal site (SWDS) receiving a mill's EFB output [1, 2, 3]. The present article addresses the other, and more widespread, disposal pattern: dispersed dumping of EFB in the plantation fields. Rather than being held in one permanent dump beside the mill, the EFB is trucked out into the estate and left in piles and windrows along the field roads, periodically rotated between locations.

EFB is a bulky, wet, acidic residue that costs money to handle and is produced faster than most mills can use it, so the field windrows are shallow, frequently disturbed and dispersed across the estate. The

purpose of this article is twofold: first, to document, from direct field observation, how a dumped EFB pile decomposes and when in that process methane is generated; and second, to convert those observations into a defensible emission figure using the UNFCCC first-order decay methodology. A central finding is that the rate at which the piles actually decompose is far higher than the methodology assumes, and the consequences of that discrepancy for the emission estimate are set out in Sections 6 and 7.

2. EFB Generation and Disposal

Empty fruit bunch is the residue left after the oil-bearing fruits are stripped from the fresh fruit bunch (FFB) at the mill. The FFB is sterilised under steam at about 143 °C for some 45 minutes, the fruits are threshed and pressed for oil, and the remaining bunch — the EFB — is discarded. A standard 60 t h⁻¹ mill receives roughly 900 to 1,000 tonnes of FFB per day; with EFB comprising about 23 to 25 % of FFB by weight, this yields on the order of 190 to 230 tonnes of moist EFB per day, or an annualised average of approximately 66,676 tonnes per year for a representative mill.

A minority of mills use part of the EFB as supplementary boiler fuel, press it for residual juice, or compost a portion; but the vast majority simply dump it at the most convenient location. Field disposal takes several forms: tipping in a fresh pile on the side of a field road, adding to an existing windrow, or spreading the material out along a windrow, sometimes with mechanical assistance from tractors. Better-managed estates rotate the receiving locations. The common feature is that the EFB is left in place to decompose, with no aeration, processing or gas management.

Figure 1. An oil palm empty fruit bunch: a fibrous mass of an inner pith core and outer frondlets, weighing roughly 1 to 2 kg, which is discarded after the fruits are removed at the mill.

3. Field Survey: Materials and Methods

Seven EFB dumping sites in West Kalimantan, Indonesia, were surveyed between September and November 2024. At each site the following were recorded: the estimated age of the dumped EFB; the state of decomposition (aerobic or anaerobic); the dimensions of the pile (length, width and height, measured with a tape); the in-pile methane concentration; and a photograph. The sites spanned the full range of decomposition, from freshly tipped material to windrows close to a year old, so that the

complete decomposition sequence could be reconstructed from piles of different ages observed at one time.

Methane was measured with a Tadeto CGD02A handheld methane detector (range 50 to 50,000 ppm). A hole was first made in the pile with a wooden stick, and the detector probe — approximately 30 cm long — was inserted into the hole before the reading was taken. This sampled the gas within the body of the pile rather than at its surface, where dilution by air would otherwise mask the methane.

4. The Decomposition Sequence

The field observations reveal that a dumped EFB pile decomposes through a consistent sequence of stages, and — importantly for the emission accounting — that methane is generated only during part of that sequence.

Fresh EFB arrives from the mill still warm and steaming and is tipped into a large pile; at this point no decomposition has begun. Within several days to a month the pile is colonised by fungi, whose filaments extend through the material, and self-heats as aerobic micro-organisms break down the readily available organic matter. Throughout this aerobic phase no methane is emitted. Over the following one to two months the pile shrinks and compacts, the fungal growth recedes and the temperature normalises, but anaerobic conditions have not yet formed.

Figure 2. Freshly dumped EFB. The material is warm and undecomposed on arrival from the mill.

Figure 3. Fungal colonisation during the aerobic phase. Self-heating and fungal filaments are characteristic of aerobic decomposition, which produces carbon dioxide rather than methane.

From roughly the second to third month the interior of the pile transitions to anaerobic decomposition, and methane begins to form. This was confirmed by direct measurement: in a three-month-old pile less than 0.7 m high, 8 m wide and 6 m long (volume-to-surface-area ratio 1.02), methane was detected within the pile at up to 6,076 ppm. In an older pile of about four months — 8 m long, 5 m wide and 1 m high — anaerobic conditions were well established and methane was measured at up to 24,866 ppm, or 2.5 % by volume (Figure 5). The same pile, revisited a month later, was still anaerobic.

Figure 4. An anaerobic EFB windrow during the methane-generating phase. Palm fronds have been laid over part of the windrow.

Figure 5. In-pile methane concentration of 24,866 ppm (2.5 % v/v) measured with the handheld detector inside a four-month-old anaerobic EFB pile.

By nine to twelve months the windrow is well decomposed: it has lost much of its volume and height, methane is no longer detectable, and the absence of fresh fungal growth indicates that aerobic organisms have not recolonised the residue. What remains is largely tough, woody lignin that neither aerobic nor anaerobic organisms readily digest. The methane-generating window for any given batch of EFB is therefore bounded — beginning around the second month and ending by the ninth — even though a site that receives fresh EFB continually will contain material at all stages at once and so emit methane continuously.

5. Monitoring Results

The seven surveyed sites are summarised in Table 1. Methane was detected only at the sites in the anaerobic stage (sites 1 and 7), at 24,866 ppm and 6,076 ppm respectively; the fresh and aerobic sites returned no methane, consistent with the decomposition sequence above. Several piles had a volume-to-surface-area ratio below 1.5, yet still developed anaerobic interiors and emitted methane — a point of relevance to how a solid waste disposal site is defined in the methodology (Section 7).

Site	Age (months)	Methane (ppm)	Volume : surface-area	State of decomposition
1	3-6	24,866	1.03	Anaerobic
2	2	0	1.0	Aerobic
3	0	0	1.0	Fresh
4	1	0	1.34	New
5	2	0	0.5	Aerobic
6	9-12	0	0.75	Decomposed
7	3	6,076	1.02	Anaerobic

Table 1. Field survey of seven EFB dumping sites in West Kalimantan, Indonesia, September-November 2024.

6. Methane Emissions from Field Dumping

The methane released from dumped EFB is quantified with the UNFCCC Methodological Tool 04, “Emissions from solid waste disposal sites” [4], which applies the IPCC first-order decay (FOD) model [5]. EFB is treated as garden-type waste, the category the methodology provides for this kind of agro-residue. The methane generated in year y is:

$$BE_{CH_4,SWDS,y} = \varphi_y \cdot (1 - f_y) \cdot GWP_{CH_4} \cdot (1 - OX) \cdot (16/12) \cdot F \cdot DOC_{f,y} \cdot MCF_y \cdot \sum_x [W_x \cdot DOC_j \cdot e^{(-k(y-x))} \cdot (1 - e^{(-k)})]$$

where the summation runs over each year of disposal x from the first ($x = 1$) to the year of interest ($x = y$). The bracketed term is the methane-generating organic carbon dumped in year x that has not yet decayed by year y ; it is summed over all past years and multiplied by the factors that convert decayed carbon to atmospheric methane. The parameters used for field-dumped EFB are listed in Table 2; they follow the methodology defaults for a shallow, unmanaged disposal site, with the disposed mass set to the annual EFB output of a representative 60 t h⁻¹ mill.

Symbol	Parameter	Value	Basis / note
W_x	EFB dumped per year (t)	66,676	Annual output, 60 t/h mill
DOC_j	Degradable organic carbon fraction of EFB	0.20	Tool 04, garden-type waste
$DOC_{f,y}$	Fraction of DOC that decomposes	0.157	Methanogenic potential of EFB

k	Decay rate (yr ⁻¹)	0.17 / 1.0	Methodology default vs observed
MCF_y	Methane correction factor	0.40	Unmanaged shallow disposal
F	Methane fraction of landfill gas	0.50	Tool 04 default
OX	Oxidation factor	0.10	Tool 04 default
f_y	Fraction of methane captured	0	Open dumping, no capture
GWP_CH4	Global warming potential of CH ₄	28	IPCC AR5, 100-year
φ_y	Model correction factor	0.64	Tool 04, with uncertainty factor

Table 2. UNFCCC Tool 04 parameters used to quantify methane emissions from field-dumped EFB.

The decay rate k is the parameter at issue. The methodology assigns a default of 0.17 yr^{-1} to this waste category, but the field survey shows the piles substantially decomposed within nine to twelve months, implying an effective rate close to 1.0 yr^{-1} (Section 7). Both values are therefore carried through the calculation below so that their effect can be compared directly.

6.1 The single-pile emission profile

Consider first the EFB dumped in one year alone, left to rot undisturbed. The emission peaks in the first year and then decays exponentially as the organic carbon is consumed. For the first year the summation reduces to a single term:

$$BE_{\text{year } 1} = 0.6752 \cdot W_x \cdot DOC_j \cdot (1 - e^{-(k)})$$

At the methodology rate $k = 0.17 \text{ yr}^{-1}$ this gives $0.6752 \cdot 66,676 \cdot 0.20 \cdot 0.157 \approx 1,408 \text{ t CO}_2\text{e}$ in the first year, falling to about $1,190 \text{ t CO}_2\text{e}$ in the second and roughly $300 \text{ t CO}_2\text{e}$ by the tenth — the slow tail of a pile assumed to take well over a decade to break down. At the observed rate $k = 1.0 \text{ yr}^{-1}$ the first-year emission is instead $0.6752 \cdot 66,676 \cdot 0.20 \cdot 0.632 \approx 5,690 \text{ t CO}_2\text{e}$, with the pile essentially exhausted within three to four years. The total methane released by the pile is the same in both cases — decay rate changes only the timing, not the quantity — but the observed rate concentrates it into the first few years rather than spreading it across two decades (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Emission profile of a single year's dumped EFB (66,676 t) at the methodology decay rate ($k = 0.17 \text{ yr}^{-1}$) and the observed rate ($k = 1.0 \text{ yr}^{-1}$). The same total emission is released either slowly over two decades or rapidly within a few years.

6.2 Emission under continuous dumping

In practice a mill dumps fresh EFB every year, so the emission in any year is the sum of the still-decaying contributions of all previous years' dumping plus that of the current year. Both decay rates lead to the same steady-state annual emission — approximately 9,000 t CO₂e per year — because at steady state the carbon dumped each year equals the carbon decaying each year regardless of how fast any individual pile breaks down. What differs is how quickly that steady state is reached: at the observed rate the dump reaches its full ~9,000 t CO₂e per year within about three years, whereas at the methodology rate it takes roughly two decades to climb there (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Annual methane emission under continuous year-on-year dumping of 66,676 t of EFB. Both decay rates approach the same steady state of about 9,000 t CO₂e per year, but the observed rate reaches it far sooner.

6.3 Effect on the cumulative emission

The difference in timing has a real consequence over a finite crediting period. Because the methodology rate defers a large share of each year's emission into later years — and, for the most recent dumping, beyond the accounting window entirely — it reports a lower cumulative emission than the observed rate over the same thirty years. Summed over a thirty-year period of continuous dumping, the methodology rate gives a cumulative of approximately 222,000 t CO₂e, whereas the observed rate gives approximately 265,000 t CO₂e — about 19 % higher (Figure 8). The methodology, in other words, does not merely mis-time the emissions; applied over a fixed crediting period it understates them, because it assumes carbon is still slowly decaying years after the field evidence shows the pile has already stabilised.

Figure 8. Cumulative methane emission over a thirty-year period of continuous dumping. The observed decay rate yields about 19 % more emissions over the crediting period than the methodology default, which defers part of the emission beyond the window.

Quantity	k = 0.17 yr ⁻¹ (methodology)	k = 1.0 yr ⁻¹ (observed)	Difference
Single pile, first-year emission (t CO ₂ e)	1,408	5,690	+304 %
Time to ~95 % decomposed (single pile)	~18 years	~3 years	—
Steady-state annual emission (t CO ₂ e/yr)	~9,000	~9,000	same
Years to reach 90 % of steady state	~14 years	~2 years	—
30-year cumulative emission (t CO ₂ e)	221,800	264,900	+19 %

Table 3. Effect of the decay-rate assumption on the field-dumping emission estimate.

7. Discussion

The survey settles the central empirical question: field-dumped EFB does generate methane, and it does so even in piles with a volume-to-surface-area ratio below 1.5. Methane appears once a pile enters its anaerobic phase, from around the second to third month, and persists until the material is largely decomposed at about nine months. The aerobic head-start — the first one to two months, during which fungal, oxygen-using decomposition produces only carbon dioxide — means that the methane-generating window for any single batch is finite, but a site fed continuously with fresh EFB holds material at every stage simultaneously and so emits methane year-round.

The central methodological problem the survey exposes concerns the decay rate. The first-order decay model is only as good as its rate constant k , and the value the methodology assigns to this waste category, 0.17 yr^{-1} , implies a half-life of about four years and near-complete decomposition only after fifteen to twenty years. The field evidence directly contradicts this: every site observed was substantially decomposed within nine to twelve months, with methane no longer detectable and only woody lignin residue remaining. That timescale corresponds to an effective decay rate close to 1.0 yr^{-1} — roughly six times the methodology default — and is consistent with reports from other authors on the rapid breakdown of EFB in tropical field conditions.

The effect of this discrepancy is set out in Section 6 and summarised in Table 3. The decay rate does not change the total quantity of methane a given mass of EFB ultimately releases, nor the long-run steady-state annual emission of about 9,000 t CO₂e per year, because those are fixed by the mass dumped and the fraction of its carbon that becomes methane. What the decay rate governs is the timing. At the true, faster rate the emission is released within the first few years of each pile's life rather than dribbling out over two decades; under continuous dumping the dump reaches its full emission rate within about three years instead of twenty. Over a fixed thirty-year crediting period this raises the cumulative emission by about 19 % — from roughly 222,000 to 265,000 t CO₂e — because the methodology's slow decay defers part of the emission beyond the accounting window. Applied as written, therefore, the methodology not only mis-times the emissions but understates them over any finite crediting period, and it would correspondingly understate the credit due to a project that diverts the EFB. The decay-rate parameter for EFB warrants revision toward the observed value.

Two further points follow for the methodology and its application. First, the definition of a solid waste disposal site is, in practice, tied to geometry through the volume-to-surface-area ratio; the field evidence that piles below the conventional ratio still turn anaerobic and emit methane argues for lowering that threshold so that ordinary field windrows are not excluded from the accounting. Second, at national scale the magnitude is not trivial: with Indonesia producing of order forty-five million tonnes of palm oil per year and a comparable tonnage of EFB, the implied methane emission from EFB dumping is on the order of several million tonnes of CO₂e per year — a meaningful share of national emissions, and a correspondingly meaningful liability were it to be priced under an emissions-trading scheme or a border carbon adjustment. Pricing these emissions would create a direct incentive for mills to adopt the alternatives to dumping, such as composting or anaerobic digestion.

8. Conclusion

Field dumping of oil palm empty fruit bunch in the plantation, the most common disposal practice in the industry, is a genuine methane source. Direct survey of seven sites in West Kalimantan confirms that dumped EFB becomes anaerobic from the second to third month and emits methane — measured at up to 24,866 ppm within the piles — until it is largely decomposed by about the ninth month. Quantified with the UNFCCC first-order decay methodology and EFB classified as garden-type waste, a representative 60 t h⁻¹ mill dumping about 66,676 t of EFB per year settles to a steady state of approximately 9,000 t CO_{2e} per year under continuous dumping. The survey's most consequential finding is that the piles decompose far faster than the methodology assumes — within a year rather than over two decades — so that the appropriate decay rate is close to 1.0 rather than 0.17 yr⁻¹. This does not change the steady-state annual emission, but it front-loads the release and raises the cumulative emission over a thirty-year crediting period by about a fifth, meaning the methodology as written understates the emission and the credit that diverting EFB would earn. Together with the baseline established in the previous article, this fixes the emission reference for the principal EFB disposal routes, against which the climate benefit of diverting EFB to composting, digestion or conversion can be measured; and it indicates that the methodology's decay rate, and its volume-to-surface-area definition of a disposal site, deserve revision for this feedstock.

Author Contributions

D.S.: conceptualisation, methodology, validation, investigation, writing — original draft. A.B.: review and editing.

Funding

This research received no external funding.

Acknowledgements

We are grateful to the staff who facilitated access to the EFB dumping areas in West Kalimantan, Indonesia.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

References

- [1] Spagnuolo, D. & Broughton, A. (2026). Basic Properties of Oil Palm Empty Fruit Bunch (EFB): Dry Solids, Moisture and a Comparative Review of Compositional, Proximate, Ultimate, Calorific and Inorganic Data. Article 1 of this series.
- [2] Spagnuolo, D. & Broughton, A. (2026). Hydrolysate Production from Oil Palm Empty Fruit Bunch (EFB): Field-Scale Bucket Testing of Hot-Water Oil Stripping, Alkaline Hydrolysis and Enzymatic Saccharification. Article 2 of this series. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20520978>

[3] Spagnuolo, D. & Broughton, A. (2026). Baseline Methane Emissions from a Large Solid Waste Disposal Site Receiving Oil Palm Empty Fruit Bunch (EFB). Article 3 of this series.

[4] UNFCCC CDM Executive Board. Methodological Tool 04: Emissions from solid waste disposal sites. Clean Development Mechanism, UNFCCC.

[5] IPCC (2006). 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories, Volume 5, Chapter 3: Solid Waste Disposal. Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change.

[6] Lim, K. C. & Zakarah, A. R. (2000). Journal of Oil Palm Research, 12(2), 55-62. (Degradable organic carbon of empty fruit bunch.)